

THE ROLE OF ONLINE TRANSLATORS IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Today, the professions and hobbies of many people are closely interrelated with foreign languages. To facilitate their activities, many of them study another language, however, not everyone has such an opportunity. The solution to the problem is such a phenomenon as an online translator.

The use of online translators helps people in the following cases: correspond with foreign friends, discover new languages, do exercises in English, study, prepare for negotiations with foreigners for work, and much more.

The first experiment, which laid the foundation for future online translators, took place in 1954. It was prepared by Georgetown University in collaboration with IBM. During this procedure, a fully automatic translation of more than 60 sentences from Russian into English was demonstrated. This presentation had a positive impact on the development of machine translation in the next 12 years, when it became interested in countries such as England, Bulgaria, the GDR, Italy, China, France, Germany, Japan, and other countries; in the same 1954 and the USSR. The progenitor of online translators knew only 250 words, and 6 grammatical rules, and could translate only the simplest phrases. However, this experiment gave an impetus to research in this industry. The demonstration was widely covered by the media, and the scientific world found its results more than satisfactory. The governments of some states, primarily the United States, have decided to start investing in the field of computational linguistics.

Many people have a certain stereotype regarding online translators that it is impossible to translate large fragments of text efficiently. They are sure that the text

will be distorted in such a translation, and it will be difficult for the recipient to understand it. However, now this stereotype is starting to break down. Many users of online translators are convinced in practice that current online translators can translate not only a word or sentence, but also large phrases, dialogues, articles, texts, and various types of correspondence in a high-quality and understandable way. The most popular language that is translated with the help of online translators is English. Today, users can use both free versions of online translators and buy more advanced versions for a certain amount.

The relevance of this topic lies in the fact that most people are interested in translating words and individual texts using online translators, as it is familiar, gratuitous, and fast.

For research on the use of online translators in the process of learning English, it is necessary to refer to the definition of the concept of an online translator. An online translator is an electronic dictionary that is available only when connected to the Internet. Today, online translators are a very popular phenomenon on the internet.

Such services are easy to find on the Internet. Online translators are often installed on popular sites, some are located on separate sites, and sometimes they are released as applications.

Each of the online translators has a simple interface. It is usually implemented in the following order: Copy) - Paste (Paste) – and select (for example, Russian - German). This program works by selecting dictionaries of interlanguage grammar and this process occurs when the user sends a request to the server. Usually, you can use this service absolutely for free.

After studying the vast expanses of the Internet, we concluded that there are a huge number of online translators. Yandex, Google, Bing, Promt, Linqvo, Anplex, Microsoft Translator, Babel Fish Translation, Worldlingo Multilingual Translator)....

To determine the quality of online translators, we turned to the classification method. Our task was to determine which online translator was easier to use and

closest to the original text. After studying the methodological literature, we identified the criteria for evaluating quality and called them functional capabilities (the ability to reproduce text, connect special dictionaries, translate web pages, auto-detection of the source text, the number of supported languages, word transliteration service, restrictions on the amount of text entered, the possibility of simultaneous translation, spell checking). It will take a long time to consider each position, so we will look at some of them.

1. Google Translator is a free translation service that provides instant translations using 57 different languages. It can translate words, sentences, and webpages from and into any of the supported languages. When a Google Translator creates a translation, it searches for templates in hundreds of millions of documents to provide the best translation. When templates are found in documents that have already been translated by people, Google Translator can make intelligent assumptions to select the appropriate translation. The process of searching for patterns in large volumes of text is called "statistical machine translation". Since translations are performed by computers, not all of their results will be perfect. The more documents translated by people that Google Translator can analyze in a particular language are used, the better the translation quality will be. That is why the accuracy of translation in different languages sometimes differs.

Number of languages: Google translates from/to Arabic, English, Bulgarian, Chinese (Simplified), Chinese (Traditional), Croatian, Czech, Danish, Dutch, Finnish, French, German, Greek, Hindi, Italian, Korean, Japanese, Norwegian, Polish, Romanian, Russian, Spanish, Swedish, Portuguese.

2. Yandex Translator - Easy of access and operation: Simple design. Registration

is not required. The system can translate text and web pages. It is possible to load the page. The interface is Russian. Yandex translator translates from/to Dutch, English, French, German, Italian, Portuguese, Spanish, Russian, Swedish. Thematic databases: 21 of them - general vocabulary, automobiles and technology, aviation and space, chemistry, household topics, computers and data processing, earth

science, economics and business, electronics, food industry, law, natural sciences, mathematics, mechanical engineering, medicine, metallurgy, military, maritime and shipping, photography and optics, physics and atomic energy, political science. The availability of databases significantly improves the quality of translation.

From the above, we can conclude that an online translator is a good assistant for learning English.

Literature:

1. Аракин В.Д. История английского языка.-М., Высшая школа,1968
2. Бархударов Л. С. Язык и перевод. М., 1975
3. Комиссаров В.Н. Современное переводоведение. М.: ЭТС, 2008
4. Словарь иностранных слов. М.: Русский язык, 2010.
5. Энциклопедический справочник. Все страны мира. М.: Вече, 2004.
6. <http://translate.google.com>
7. <http://translate.yandex.ru/>
8. <http://www.translate.ru>.